

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DISCONTINUITIES IN AIRCRAFT COMPOSITES AS REFERENCE FLAWS FOR GUIDED WAVE BASED ULTRASONIC TESTING

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ABSTRACT

The main motivation of this work is to provide a contribution to reference aircraft composite samples suitable for the calibration and comparison of non-destructive quantitative evaluation techniques using ultrasonic guided waves as well as to establish ways to create such samples with artificial flaws that reproduce the most common defects in aircraft composites. Those are porosity, which is the most common defect that happens during the manufacturing process, whereas delamination due to impacts happens mostly in operation time. Both kinds of defects deteriorate the mechanical properties of the composite material and have to be found, sized, and located by non-destructive testing. In this paper methods for preparation and characterization of porosity and delaminations in composites are presented and compared, which can help on the way to realize a mock-up for guided wave testing accepted by the aircraft industry. X-ray computed tomography provides damage maps for the creation of numerical models individually for different damage types.

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Ultrasonic testing (UT) techniques resting upon bulk waves are well established in industry. Therefore, today, many international standards accepted by the aircraft industry exist. These techniques are also performed on aircraft composites like GLARE (glass laminate aluminium reinforced epoxy) and carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites.

This is not the case for ultrasonic testing techniques that are using guided ultrasonic waves (GUW)—although guided waves have been used successfully in structural health monitoring (SHM) systems to detect damage in isotropic and composite materials with simple and complex geometry [1]. One reason for this situation is the lack of reference and calibration samples for the verification of the guided wave based techniques [2]. In addition, established and approved methods to create artificial discontinuities or flaws in aircraft composites are also lacking. Kissing disbonds and weak bonds pose particular challenges. A promising approach to generate kissing disbonds and weak bonds in GLARE is the use of the ElectRelease[®] system [3].

Hence, the main motivation of this work is to define reference aircraft composite samples suitable for the calibration and comparison of non-destructive quantitative evaluation techniques using ultrasonic guided waves as well as to establish ways to create such samples with artificial flaws that simulate and emulate the most common defects in aircraft composites.

Porosity is the most common defect that happens during the manufacturing process of aircraft composites [4]. Delamination in aircraft composites due to impacts is the most common defect that happens during service life [5]. Both kinds of defects deteriorate the mechanical properties of the composite material and have to be found, sized and located by non-destructive testing (NDT) [6]. The ultrasonic test equipment shall be capable to detect a minimum defect dimension of 6 mm, e.g. 6 mm × 6mm, or 6 mm diameter. Any detected defects of and above this size must be recorded.

In this paper methods for preparation and characterization of porosity and delaminations in GLARE and carbon fibre reinforced polymer composite (CFRP) plates are presented and compared. This work can help on the way to realize a mock-up for guided ultrasonic wave testing accepted by the aircraft industry.

2 FABRICATION OF SAMPLES

Two basic types of specimens were prepared in the form of plates: on the one hand quasi-isotropic laminates made of CFRP and on the other hand GLARE. Different artificial defects were incorporated during the lay-up. In the following, at first only the plate manufacturing without the artificial discontinuities is described.

The quasi-isotropic laminates are composed of 8, 16, 27 or 32 plies of HexPly[®] M21-34-268T800S-ATL300LAU unidirectional prepreg. The samples used for UT were covered by SM905M-68%-ECS73GSM-300ATL lightning protection plies. The laminates were fabricated with a hot press vacuum bag process, using the process parameters: curing for 120 min at 180 °C under a pressure of 8 bar, then cooling down to 60 °C by convection under continuous pressure. The resulted plates have a size of 600 mm × 600 mm with a thickness of 2 mm, 4 mm, 7 mm or 8 mm.

The GLARE composites are composed of five aluminium (Al) sheets for aircrafts with a thickness of 0.4 mm and eight layers of glass fibre prepreg. For the materialographic study, plates of 500 mm × 500 mm × 4 mm in size, made from primed aluminium 2024 T3 and aerospace qualified bidirectional glass fiber (GF) prepreg EHG250-68-37 T2 100 with 8-H satin weaver style were fabricated with a hot press vacuum bag process. The total thickness results from 0.25 mm thick prepreg layers, aluminium layers of 0.4 mm thickness each, and a lay-up according to the impact tolerant standard GLARE grade GLARE5, in fact 5/4-0.4 [Al/GF/GF/Al/GF/GF/Al/GF/GF/Al/GF/GF/Al] and non-standard GLARE [Al/GF/GF/GF/GF/Al/GF/GF/GF/GF/Al/GF/GF/GF/GF/Al] with a 4/3-0.4 lay-up configuration as shown in Figure 4. The process parameters of the hot press vacuum bag process were: curing for 40 min at 155 °C under a pressure of 4 bar and cooling down to 60 °C by convection under continuous pressure.

3 PREPARATION OF DISCONTINUITIES

3.1 Delaminations

Delaminations are simulated either using release film inserts of different sizes or by local application of release agents on the prepreg or aluminium sheets. The materials were placed on predefined positions during lay-up between two prepreg layers or between a prepreg and an aluminium layer.

Commonly, 0.05 mm thick fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) film patches and 0.07 mm thick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film patches were used in the aircraft industry to reproduce artificial defects in reference panels for UT. In this work 0.05 mm thick Wrightlon[®] 5200 release film patches of different sizes were used to create artificial delaminations. The material type of Wrightlon[®] 5200 is ethylene tetrafluoroethylene (ETFE) a high performance fluoropolymer.

The release agents Marbocote TRE 45 ECO, LOCTITE[®] FREKOTE 55NC[™], Chemlease[®] IC25 and common lubricating grease were used to create disbonds without additional film patches. The materials were applied by brushing.

3.2 Porosity

Increased global porosity adjusts via manipulation of process parameter settings. Artificial local porosity is simulated by local application of different foaming agents or filler materials on the prepreg.

The materials citric acid, cream of tartar, baking powder, PORAVER[®] expanded glass with grain sizes from 0.04 mm to 0.125 mm, easycomposites[™] thixotropic fumed silica powder, water, xylol, toluol, TRACEL[®] 4170 ACR, TRACEL[®] PO 4207, TRACEL[®] PO 4207 and three component foaming resin system consisting of the blowing agent EP 50, the foaming resin hardener FH 37 and the epoxy foaming resin FR 37 from Suter Kunststoffe AG were used in preliminary tests to reproduce localized porosity in 2 mm thick composite plates.

The granulates which are citric acid, cream of tartar, baking powder, PORAVER[®] and the silica powder were applied with a laboratory microspatula on the prepreg surface during lay-up. The citric acid was further pulverized with a pestle in order to achieve a more homogeneous application of the substance to the prepreg. The liquids water, xylol and toluol were applied drop by drop with a laboratory disposable pipette on the prepreg surface during lay-up. The materials in pellet form are TRACEL[®] 4170 ACR, TRACEL[®] PO 4207 and TRACEL[®] PO 4207. A few pellets of each material were laid down with tweezers on the prepreg surface. The three component foaming resin system was used as follows: the used mixtures of foam resin blowing agent were 100:1, 100:3 and 100:5. The resins with the blowing agent were prepared in the mixing ratio 10:4 according to weight. The foaming resin system was applied by localized brushing.

4 CHARACTERIZATION OF SAMPLES

4.1 Materialography

The porosity of different samples was obtained, evaluated quantitatively and compared using optical microscopy. Figure 1 shows a cross section of a GLARE sample with increased porosity. In this case the porosity was increased by lowering the pressure during curing.

4.2 X-ray measurements

X-ray measurements and X-ray computed tomography (XCT) scans were performed on a Phoenix v|tome|x m (research edition) manufactured by GE in order to characterize the deliberately made defects. Figure 2 shows a X-ray image of a laminate with an artificial delamination reproduced with an ETFE patch with a size of 50 mm × 20 mm. Figure 3 shows a result of a XCT scan of a composite sample with local porosity made with citric acid. Hence, 5×10^{-5} g/mm² of pestled citric acid and 100:5 mixtures of foam resin blowing agent provide useful results for the creation of porosity. Figure 4 shows a result of a XCT scan of a GLARE sample with porosity and a delamination made by a film patch. Delaminations due to release agents and lubricating grease were not detectable by X-ray measurements.

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of a cross section of a GLARE sample with increased porosity

Figure 2: X-ray image of an artificial delamination with a size of 50 mm × 20 mm

Figure 3: X-ray computed tomography image of localized porosity

Figure 4: XCT image of 4 mm thick GLARE sample consisting of four aluminium layers and three layers of glass fibre prepregs. An artificial defect in the form of a circular ETFE patch insert of 10 mm in diameter was embedded in the laminate. In addition to the insert, the porosity in the epoxy resin is increased.

The incorporation of such XCT damage maps into models for numerical simulations of guided ultrasonic waves improves understanding of the influence of defects on the propagation of GUW. Damage models can be created individually for different damage types, i.e. for delamination and debonding between metal and composite layers, and for localized porosity, for later implementation in finite element models. One helpful advantage of such numerical models is that individual effects of wave propagation and waveguide can be switched on and off to make the NDT more efficient.

4.3 Characterization of samples with ultrasonic testing

Besides materialography and X-ray measurements the specimens were also examined by UT techniques using bulk waves and guided waves. All of the used quasi-isotropic samples are covered with a lightning protection layer.

The ultrasonic bulk waves were applied in an impulse echo configuration to the processed samples in an immersion tank filled with water. The reflected signals were analysed in a time interval after the entrance echo [7].

For the investigations with guided waves, both A_0 and S_0 Lamb wave modes were used. These were excited with EMAT (Electro Magnetic Acoustic Transducer) probes as pure modes and with a well-defined operating point in the test object [8], [9], [10]. The propagation of Lamb waves is influenced by inhomogeneities in the test objects and mode conversion processes take place, whereby the frequency is constant [11]. Since the receiving transducers are sensitive to many modes and a wide operating range, these changes can be locally detected and analysed.

The operation parameters for both UT techniques are summarized in Table 1. In both cases the surface of the specimen was completely scanned with a pitch of 1 mm to 2 mm in x and in y direction. The origins of the volume waves and the guided wave inspection differ slightly from each other.

Parameter	Bulk wave	Guided wave
Wave type	Normal incident longitudinal wave	Lamb waves (A_0 , S_0)
Operation frequency	4 MHz	200 kHz to 400 kHz
Transducer	Piezo	EMAT

Table 1: UT parameters

The following figures show exemplarily the results of the ultrasonic examinations for local delaminations both near the surface and close to the centre line of the plate as well as for spatially limited porosity. Each defect area is displayed as C-scan image for bulk wave and guided wave UT (see Figure 5 to Figure 7).

Figure 5: UT results for a 40 mm \times 50 mm area of porosity (left: bulk wave, right: guided wave)

Figure 6: UT results for a 10 mm \times 20 mm area of delamination in surface near layers (left: bulk wave, right: guided wave)

Figure 7: UT results for 10 mm \times 20 mm area of delamination in central layers (left: bulk wave, right: guided wave)

Both defect types can be reliably detected with UT for defect areas down to $5\text{ mm} \times 5\text{ mm}$ and smaller, also the size of the defect area can be clearly identified. But a determination of the depth position of the delamination in the composite material is not yet possible with the guided wave inspection technique.

Further, the guided waves of the A_0 mode are particularly sensitive to delaminations, while porosity can be better detected with the S_0 mode. In addition, it should also be noted that guided wave inspection using the EMAT technique does not need any couplant. This makes it much easier to handle compared to conventional ultrasonic technology based on piezoelectric probes.

The defect types produced by the release agent LOCTITE® FREKOTE 55NC™ and common lubricating grease were detectable by UT using bulk waves, whereas imperfections caused by the release agents Chemlease® IC25 and Marbocote TRE 45 ECO were not detectable by UT using bulk waves. So far, none of them could be detected using guided waves.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results show that artificial defects like delaminations and porosity can be induced by several approaches. Film patches and the release agent LOCTITE® FREKOTE 55NC™ can be used to emulate reference delamination flaws. Citric acid and mixtures of foam resin blowing agent of the foaming resin system consisting of the blowing agent EP 50, the foaming resin hardener FH 37 and the epoxy foaming resin FR 37 are promising to cause local porosity.

All of these artificial flaws are detectable with UT using bulk waves. Delaminations reproduced by film patches and artificial porosity are also detectable by XCT. The incorporation of XCT damage maps into models for numerical simulations of guided ultrasonic waves improves understanding of the influence of defects on the propagation of GUW. The results show that the GUW of the A_0 mode are particularly sensitive to delaminations, while porosity can better be detected with the S_0 mode. In addition, it should be also noted that guided wave inspection using the EMAT technique does not need any couplant. This makes it much easier to handle compared to conventional ultrasonic technology based on piezoelectric probes.

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Figure 8: Logo with additional information

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